

Une

Language

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About the names

- **IoTg**
This is formed by the prefix IoT (Internet of Things) and the letter “g”, which comes from Glue. Meaning that IoTg aims to be the Glue for the IoT. All other names, are referred in one or another way to the idea of “Glue”. It is the name of the whole ecosystem (the platform): the language and all the tools around.
- **Une**
In Spanish language it means “what joins”. It is the name of the language.
- **Tape**
Glue exists also in the form of a tape: used mainly when wrapping gifts. It is the name of the transpiler (a special type of compiler).
- **Stick**
Glue-sticks are mainly used by kids. It is the name of the Execution Environment.
- **Glue**
This is the traditional form of presentation: liquid. It is the name of the IDE (Integrated Development Environment).
- **Gum**
This is an ancient form of glue. It is the name of the monitoring tool.

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Chapter 1

Overview

Une

Introduction

“*Une*” is the language for the IoTg Platform. *Une* was designed with simplicity in mind: it is so easy that anyone with basic concepts of a spreadsheet can learn *Une* in one single day, at least its basics, but enough to manage a family house.

Une is very close to a natural language (these languages that we use to communicate with other human beings). Although this handbook uses *Une* in English, it can be “translated” into other languages (Spanish, German, French, Chinese, ..); later we will explain how to do it.

A sneak preview

Here is how to say: “when the alarm is on and any door is opened, then send a message to my Telegram¹”.

```
WHEN alarm IS ON AND ANY door IS OPEN  
THEN MyTelegram SET "DANGER! Intruders at home"
```

How is this book organized

1. We will start explaining some basic concepts.
2. Next we will go through several examples, increasing the complexity.
3. And we will end with the formal description of the language.

How to learn *Une* in one day

If you are familiar with any spreadsheet (MS-Office Excel, LibreOffice Calc, etc.), then you can learn *Une* basics -enough to manage a home installation- in one day.

There are lots of examples under the folder “examples”. The examples are orderer in a increasing complexity order, being 1 the simplest. These examples is one of the two key pieces you need learn *Une*, the other key pieces is this book.

Une is the language, but to compile and run *Une* commands, you need a compiler and an executor. The compiler makes the optimizations and the translations needed by the executor to be able to execute your commands. These two tools (and other tools)

¹ <https://telegram.org>

are covered in the book titled “The IoTg Standard Platform”. Please, refer to this book to learn how to compile and execute *Une* source code.

This is our recommendation to learn *Une*:

1. Read this book Chapter 1
2. Read and run examples starting the first one, until you feel you do not fully understand the example.
3. Read this book next Chapter.
4. Read and run examples where you left it, until you feel you do not fully understand the example.
5. Go to 3.

Basic Concepts

A domotics (AKA “house automation”²) installation is basically a set of **devices** that are responsible for certain tasks: switching lights on and off, changing the temperature of a room or informing if a door or window is open or closed.

In *Une*, we declare the physical Devices that we have (at home, at office or at a factory) and we also declare how to rule them; for this, we use **rules**. We already have seen a rule in the previous example.

Before continuing:

In following pages, you’ll find lots of foot notes: this is intended. First read the pages without paying attention to foot notes. When you understand the first example, read it again the pages paying attention to the foot notes.

Devices

A Device is every electronic gadget that can inform about its estate and/or modify its estate. All gadgets that you have lets say at home, makes your “home domotic installation”. The size of the installation is not really important: it can be just a house, a building, a set of buildings or even a big factory: *Une* can handle it.

Devices are divided into 2 groups: Sensors and Actuators. An example of a **Sensor** is a thermometer, because it is a device that reads values. In this case, a thermometer

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Home_automation

reads temperature. An anemometer reads wind speed, and an hygrometer reads humidity. We call them a *read-only* device because you can not change their values.

An example of an **Actuator** is a relay, because it is a device which state can be changed: ON (closed) or OFF (open). A light is also an Actuator because we can change its state to be ON or OFF. We can know their estate and we can also change their estate, so we call them a *read-and-write* device.

But to make it simpler, we declare both types (Sensors and Actuators) with the same command keyword: **DEVICE**.

You must name every Device with an unique name. And you must associate every Device with an appropriate Driver. We will explain this with more detail along this section.

Technical hint

Some people (mostly experienced engineers) feel more comfortable using the words SENSOR for a device that is a sensor and the word ACTUATOR for a device that is an actuator, instead of using simply the DEVICE word for both. You can do it if you want because the IoTg Standard Platform (ISP) includes these two words (SENSOR and ACTUATOR) into the standard replacements *Une* file (we will talk later about the command REPLACE).

Drivers

A Driver in *Une* is very similar to the concept of a “printer driver”: you need a Driver in order to use your printer. And you will need as many drivers as different printers you have. In the same way, devices need a Driver to be able to do their job. You just need to tell *Une* which Driver to use for every device; but be careful, you must associate the right driver with the right device. If you have an Air Conditioner machine manufactured by a company named SumgSan and another by a company named KinDai, then you will need 2 drivers, one for each brand (and perhaps also the specific model).

Drivers are declared inside the **DEVICE** command: using the clause **DRIVER**. We’ll see it later.

Now we will provide some further technical explanations, if you do not feel comfortable with technical details, simply skip it.

Technical hint

Some Drivers work only with Sensors, others only with Actuators and others (less common) with both. We can ask for the value of an Actuator and we can also modify it; but when dealing with sensors, we can only ask for their values, it does not make any sense to change a Sensor's value.

If you are interested in creating your own drivers, then refer to the Drivers section in the book "The IoTg Standard Platform". Note: you will need programming knowledge in at least one of the following languages: Java, Python or JavaScript.

Rules

Meanwhile **Devices** describe the gadgets we have, **Rules** describe how devices have to interact with each others: how a domotics installation has to behave. Rules trigger actions under certain conditions (when certain conditions are satisfied).

Lets revisit the Rule shown at the beginning of this tutorial.

```
WHEN alarm IS ON AND ANY door IS OPEN
THEN MyTelegram SET "DANGER! Intruders at home"
```

We have 2 devices in the **WHEN** clause: "alarm" (it is an actuator) and "door" (it is a group of sensors³). The **WHEN** clause is satisfied only when the "alarm" is active (is ON) and any device belonging to the group of "door" devices is open.

Every time a Device changes its estate, all Rules associated⁴ with the Device will be evaluated. And when the result of the evaluation is true (when the **WHEN** clause is satisfied), all actions in the **THEN** clause will be executed (triggered). In our example, there is only one action: a message will be sent to the Device "MyTelegram" (an actuator),

3 We can define a group of devices and refer to all or any of the devices by the name of the group. We'll see how to deal with group of devices later.

4 We say a Device is associated with a Rule when the name of a Device appears in the **WHEN** clause of the Rule.

First example

OK, lets put together. To do so, we will create, a simple example, step by step. We start by declaring a Device; this Device reads computer's clock^{5 6 7}.

```
DEVICE clock
  DRIVER ClockDriver
  CONFIG
    interval SET 3s
```

We start with the device command, which is defined by the keyword **DEVICE**⁸, followed by the name of the device, in our case "clock" (it is a sensor). This is an arbitrary name that identifies uniquely every device.⁹

The next line is a clause declaring the **DRIVER** that will handle the **DEVICE**. Driver's name is given not by us but by the driver manufacturer: the driver we use in this example is provided by the ISP (IoTg Standard Platform) and its name is "ClockDriver".¹⁰

The next clause is used to configure the Driver: it uses the word **CONFIG**. Almost every Driver provides one or more parameters to configure it, some of them are mandatory (required) and others are optional, they have a value default¹¹.

In our case, this Driver Configuration accepts only one parameter, named "interval". We set the interval to 3 seconds ("s" stands for seconds, "m" for minutes, "h" for hours... We will talk about it later). This interval means that the value of the internal clock will become the value of the device every 3 seconds¹².

5 This clock reports the lapsed time since the ExEn was started (in milliseconds)

6 *Une* does not differentiate between uppercase and lowercase.

7 Indentation is optional, but most people likes it.

8 Remember **Device** and **device** will also work)

9 We can give any name to the Device as far as it follows certain simple rules that we will explain later.

10 Once again: "clockdriver" and any other combination of upper and lower letters will also work, but when having more than one word combined, it is quite common to write in upper case the first letter of each word and in lower case the rest of the word, this is known as "CamelCase" (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Camel_case). Other people prefer the use of underscores ("_") to separate words: "clock_driver", "camel_case", "these_are_four_words". It is totally up to you: *Une* is agnostic in regarding this.

11 The amount, the type and the name of the parameters depend on the manufacturer that created the Driver: you can find all this information by reading Driver declaration (check file: `{*home*}/include/common-drivers.une`)

In next command, we declare another Device. To keep things as simple as possible, we will use the “console” (it is an actuator), also known as the computer’s screen. Therefore, when we change the state of this Device, we are printing in the screen.

In the same way we did with the previous Device, we provide an unique name, not surprising it is “console”.

```
DEVICE console
  DRIVER OutputDriver
```

The next line after the name, is the **DRIVER** clause and says which one we want to use: “OutputDriver” in our case. Even if this driver admits several parameters, none of them are mandatory and the default values are OK for our purposes, so we do not need to **CONFIG** the Driver¹³.

Now the third and last command: we need to create a Rule¹⁴:

```
WHEN clock ABOVE 0
  THEN console SET "Clock value is: " + clock
```

As mentioned previously, rules are evaluated every time the associated Device (“clock” in this example) changes its value (every 3 seconds in our case) and when the result of the evaluation is true, all actions in the **THEN** clause will be executed (triggered).

In our case, our condition sets that the value of the Device named “clock” has to be above 0 (zero), therefore the **WHEN** clause will always be satisfied (will be always true). So every 3 seconds the value of the Device “clock” will change and it will be printed in the screen.

Lets explain this process in more detail:

1. Every 3 seconds, the Driver “OutputDriver” changes its Device’s value (“clock”). This Device’s value will become the amount of milliseconds elapsed

12 Every time a Device’s value is read, it becomes the value of the Device and every time a Device changes its value, all Rules associated with this Device are informed, so they can act as they are instructed.

13 FYI: the device “clock” is a sensor and device “console” is an actuator.

14 Surprisingly the word **RULE** does not appear: it will be explained later.

since the application started. This Device's Driver **reads** values, it is a *read-only* driver.

2. Every time a device's value changes, all Rules having the Device that changed in their **WHEN** clause, will be notified and they will be evaluated.
3. When Rule **WHEN** clause is satisfied, all actions in **THEN** clause will be executed. In our example, there is only one action: to set a new value for the Device named "console".
4. When we change Device's value (the console in our case), the Device notifies its Driver and the Driver will change the physical world: in our case, a message will be printed into the screen. This Device's Driver **reads** and **writes** values, it is a *read-and-write* driver.
5. The "console" device changed its estate, so all rules associated with this device will be notified. But there is no rule having "console" in their **WHEN** clause, therefore, nothing else happens.

Please, note that the value of the "clock" is preceded by the message "Clock value is: " and the plus sign. This plus sign concatenates the message with the current value of "clock". So, when we execute these 3 commands¹⁵, we will see in the screen of our computer something similar to this:

```
Clock value is: 15248
Clock value is: 18257
Clock value is: 21263
```

And that is it!

Congratulations, now you know most part of what is needed to create and manage your own domotics installation.

Well... to be totally honest, there is one more thing that is needed: some other files (provided by the ISP) have to be included. But right now, all you need to know is that you have to insert the following line in your script¹⁶:

```
INCLUDE "file://{*home*}include/standard-includes.une"
```

¹⁵ To execute Une code, it has to be compiled first, and the resulting file is passed to an Execution Environment (ExEn for short). The ISP provides a compiler named "Tape" and an ExEn named "Stick".

¹⁶ A script is a file containing a set of *Une* commands.

So, the whole script would look like this^{17 18}:

```
DEVICE clock
  DRIVER ClockDriver
  CONFIG
    interval SET 3s

DEVICE console
  DRIVER OutputDriver

WHEN clock ABOVE 0
  THEN console SET "Clock value is: " + clock

INCLUDE "file://{*home*}include/standard-includes.une"
```

There is not much more to say about Devices. You basically add as many of them as you need and you associate them with their Driver, that's all¹⁹.

On the other hand, there is much more to say about Rules; they are the key point of *Une* because Rules embed (contain, represent) the logic of the system. So, although we will talk more in the next pages about devices, we will focus in Rules.

Ruling the Rules

Une Rules has the following syntax:

```
RULE <name>
  WHEN <conditions>
  THEN <actions>
  IF <future_conditions>
```

There are clearly 2 clauses that we did not cover yet because they are optional: **RULE** and **IF**. Lets now talk about all clauses.

17 Remember: there is no special order for the commands inside the script, neither for the clauses inside the command.

18 Although you can place the INCLUDE command at any point, normally it is placed at the end of the script file.

19 There is something else: in the same way Drivers can be configured, Devices can be too. But we will talk about it later.

RULE

This clause (it also can work as a command keyword) is used when you need to give a name to the Rule, and you need to name a Rule only if you need to refer to a Rule from another Rule or from the command **SCRIPT**²⁰.

It is not frequent to name Rules, so we will cover it later.

IF

This clause is also optional and it contains future conditions: these conditions will be evaluated later in time. To illustrate this, we will take same Rule we used at the beginning of this handbook:

```
WHEN alarm IS ON AND ANY door IS OPEN
  THEN MyTelegram SET "DANGER! Intruders at home"
```

This Rule has a problem: when we arrive home, we have no time to deactivate the alarm. Lets say we set it to ON before going out. Later we come back, we open the door and the alarm is immediately triggered. But what we want is to have 30 seconds to deactivate the alarm. This can be achieved easily adding the following **IF** clause:

```
WHEN alarm IS ON AND ANY door IS OPEN
  THEN MyTelegram SET "DANGER! Intruders at home"
  IF alarm IS ON AFTER 30s
```

When the **WHEN** clause is satisfied, the action in the **THEN** clause will not be executed until the **IF** clause is satisfied, what could (or could not) occur 30 seconds after the **WHEN** was satisfied.

This would be the sequence in time:

1. The main door is opened.
2. Main door's Device changes its state.
3. The change is propagated, the Rules are informed and they are re-evaluated.

²⁰ We will cover SCRIPTs later.

4. The **WHEN** clause is satisfied (it is true) but **THEN** action is not triggered yet.
5. After 30 seconds, the **IF** clause is evaluated. If it is satisfied, the action in clause **THEN** is triggered, otherwise it will not.

THEN

Until now we placed only one action at this clause, but we can have as many actions as we want. We can separate them in two ways:

a) By writing a semicolon at the end of each action:

```
THEN MyTelegram SET "Send to Telegram"; console SET "Send to console"
```

b) By placing each action in a different line (semicolon is not needed in this case). This is the recommended way because produces clearer code:

```
THEN MyTelegram SET "Send to Telegram"  
     console     SET "Send to console"
```

Important:

Once a Rule is satisfied, all its actions will be executed, but there is no guarantee about the execution order: they are sent to the execution queue in the order they appear in the code, but it does not mean they will be finished in same order: those actions that need more time to be accomplished will finish later even if they appear prior to others that need less time. Take this into account because this can be crucial under some circumstances.

WHEN

As we said, this clause (it also can work as a command keyword) contains the “formula” (we prefer the term “expression”) that is evaluated every time a Device changes its state.

This expression is very similar to the formulas we write in spreadsheet’s cells: most of what can be written in a spreadsheet formula, can be written in **WHEN** and **IF** clauses: operators (arithmetic, relational and boolean), parenthesis, etc. If you are an

intermediate or advanced spreadsheet user, you already know a lot about *Une* expressions.

Keep in mind that **WHEN** and **IF** expressions must resolve to a Boolean value: TRUE or FALSE. In other words, the result of evaluating the expression must be a Boolean value.

Expressions are evaluated by an expression-evaluator: MS Excel has its own, LibreOffice Calc has its own and *Une* has its own. What can be done and what can not, is something that will be extensively cover later. As per now, keep in mind this: most part of what you can place in a spreadsheet formula can be placed in **WHEN** and **IF** expressions; you just change the references to other cells by the names of the Devices.

Later we will see Rules in detail, but now, this is all you need to now.

From now and until the end of this handbook, we will be more technical, but do not panic, it will be easy to be understood.

How are Rules evaluated

This is a crucial point you can not forget: every time a device changes its state, all rules associated with the device that changed (the device is part of the **WHEN** clause) will be re-evaluated.

Lets be more precise: when a device changes its state all rules are informed (they receive the device name and the new value). The rule then checks if this device is part of its **WHEN** clause, and if this is the case, the expression will be evaluated with the new value (and all other previous values it could have from other devices associated with the same rule). And finally, if the expression resolves to **TRUE**, then if there is no **IF** clause, all associated actions (**THEN** clause) will be triggered. But if there is an **IF** clause, it has to be also satisfied in order for the rule to trigger the actions.

Remember: a rule can be also unconditionally triggered by invoking it from another rule (the former rule has to be previously satisfied) or from the command **SCRIPT**.

Chapter 2

Building Blocks

Une

Commands

Introduction

Une was conceived to be as close to a natural language as possible (English, Spanish or Chinese are examples of natural languages).

A command in *Une* is very similar to what we understand by a command, but not exactly the same. In *Une*, the intention of a command is more declarative than imperative: we declare the devices and the rules that manage the devices.

Each *Une* command is written in its own paragraph²¹. In other words, to separate a command from another, we must write one (or more) empty line. It is very, very important to remember this: new lines and empty lines has a special meaning in *Une*.

Commands are composed of parts, these parts are named "clauses". Following **RULE** command:

```
RULE rule_alarm
  WHEN ANY door IS OPEN AND alarm IS ON
  THEN MyTelegram SET "DANGER! Intruders at home"
  IF alarm IS ON AFTER 30s
```

Is composed by these clauses:

- **WHEN**
- **THEN**
- **IF**

For clarity sake, it is recommended to use at least one line per clause, although we can write all clauses in the same line:

```
RULE rule_alarm WHEN ANY door IS OPEN AND alarm IS ON THEN MyTelegram
SET "DANGER! Intruders at home" IF alarm IS ON AFTER 30s
```

²¹ Taken (not literally) from Oxford dictionary: a paragraph is a group of sentences that fleshes out a single idea and is indicated by a new line.

The order of the commands in the file is not important, neither command's clauses inside a command, as far as you start the command with the keyword that represents it: **DEVICE**, **WHEN** (or **RULE**), etc.

Technical hint

Perhaps one of the languages that shares more similarities with *Une* is SQL²²: which is also a Script (command based), Declarative, Domain Specific language. It was developed by IBM to handle Relational Data Base Management Systems (RDBMS).

Une has just following 6 commands:

Command	Brief description	Used by
DEVICE	Declare physical devices	Normal users
RULE	Declare the system logic	
INCLUDE	Insert other files into current one (used by the preprocessor)	
REPLACE	Change words and symbols (used by the preprocessor)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced users • Manufacturers
SCRIPT	Execute other languages code inside the EXEn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced users • Manufacturers
DRIVER	Connect SCRIPTs with devices	Manufacturers

Summary

Une is made up of commands, commands are composed by clauses, some clauses are optional and others are not. Clauses can have sub-clauses. Clauses can also have parameters which are mostly optional (most of them have a default value). A file containing a set of commands is named a script file. The order of the commands in the file is not important, neither command's clauses inside a command, as far as you start the command with the keyword that represents it. Other files can be referred from inside a file using the **INCLUDE** command.

Lets clarify this with an example (note that in *Une*, everything after the '#' symbol is ignored: it is used to write comments):

²² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SQL>

```
DEVICE clock                # Command descriptor
    DRIVER ClockDriver      # Clause
        CONFIG              # SubClause
            interval SET 3s  # Parameter
```

Now we will summarize each command by presenting their syntax and describing them briefly. Later we will explain them in detail using examples. But first, we need to establish few...

Syntax Conventions

- Something between “<>” means that it must be replaced by its meaning.
- Something between “[]” means it is optional
- Something between “{ }” means there are several options and one of them must exist. Options are separated by “|”.
- “...” means that previous statement can be repeated as many times as needed.

One more thing: commands can have clauses with variable length arguments. As we just said, this is noted with an ellipsis: “...”. To separate the arguments, you can use a semicolon (“;”) or place each argument in a separated line²³ or both:

```
# Semicolon separated parameters
INCLUDE "file-one.une"; "file-two.une"; "file-three.une"

# Each parameter in its own line
INCLUDE "file-one.une"
        "file-two.une"
        "file-three.une"

# Both
INCLUDE "file-one.une";
        "file-two.une";
        "file-three.une"

# It is also valid to start the rest of the command in a new line
INCLUDE
    "file-one.une"
    "file-two.une"
```

²³ This is the recommended way of doing it.

```
"file-three.une"
```

Basic Commands

Following you'll find the three commands that you are familiar with: Devices and Rules.

DEVICES

Syntax:

```
DEVICE <name>
  [INIT <property> = <value> [; ...]]
  DRIVER <driver>
  [CONFIG name = <value> [; ...]]
```

Purpose:

To declare the devices that conform our physical installation.

Clauses:

- **INIT:** initializes device properties. Although different implementations of the IoTg Platform can expose different properties, the Standard (ISP) one exposes the following:
 - **Groups:** one or more comma separated group names²⁴ written between quotes.
e.g.: `groups = "doors, windows, sensors"`
 - **Delta:** Sets the minimum variation in physical device that will provoke a change in Sensor (its internal value). AKA Hysteresis²⁵. Valid only for Sensors. e.g.: `delta SET 0.1`
 - **Value:** Set device's initial value (sat only once: when the script starts). Valid only for Actuators. e.g.: `value SET ON`
- **DRIVER:** Driver's name to be used to manage the device.
- **CONFIG:** sets the DRIVER configuration. It depends on the DRIVER specified in the previous clause.

²⁴ Although it is recommended to use *Une* valid names, you can use an combination of alphabetic characters and number and even special symbols. Following are valid names for groups: a_name, a-name, @name, (00#~99)

²⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hysteresis>

Notes:

Remember: while **INIT** refers to the device, **CONFIG** refers to the Driver.

RULES*Syntax (simplified):*

```
[RULE <name>]
  WHEN <conditions>
  THEN <actions>
  [IF <future-conditions>]
```

Preconditions

```
{<device> | [ANY | ALL] <group>} <RelationalOp> <expression>
```

Actions

```
{<script> | <rule> | <device> | <group>} = <expression>
[AFTER <time_unit>] [; ...]
```

Future-conditions

```
{<device> | [ANY | ALL] <group>} <RelationalOp> <expression>
[AFTER | WITHIN] <time_unit>]
```

All together

```
WHEN <precondition> [{AND | OR | NOT} <precondition> ...]
THEN <action> [; <action> ...]
IF <future-condition> [{AND | OR | NOT} <future-condition> ...]
```

Purpose:

To declare the system logic: how the domotics installation will behave.

Clauses:

- **WHEN**: here we place the preconditions that must be satisfied for the actions to be triggered.
- **THEN**: these are actions (one or more) that will be triggered.
- **IF**: here we place future conditions that must be satisfied for the actions to be triggered. When **IF** exists, all conditions in **WHEN** and in **IF** has to be satisfied for the actions to be triggered.

Notes:

Observe that key word **RULE** (which provides Rule's name) is optional. IoTg automatically provides an unique name to Rules that has no name.

As Rules are the cornerstone of the *Une* language, we will dedicate the next chapter to them.

COMMENTS

Although comments are not commands, there are few things more useful in computer languages than comments: we, humans need to write notes not to forget things.

In *Une* language, comments start by the sharp ('#') sign: whatever we write after it, will be ignored (including the sharp sign itself, obviously).

Comments can be written at any point:

```
# I am a comment using an entire line
DEVICE clock           # I am a comment after sensor declaration
    DRIVER ClockDriver
        CONFIG
            interval SET 3s
```

An important detail: when a comment is the only thing in a line, this line is equivalent to an empty line. So, think about this:

```
# I am a comment using an entire line
DEVICE clock           # I am a comment after sensor declaration
    DRIVER ClockDriver
        # I am a comment inside a command: THIS IS WRONG!
        CONFIG
            interval SET 3s
```

The 3rd comment is occupying the whole line and it is in the middle of a command declaration (**DEVICE** in this case). So, there will be an empty line in between **DRIVER** and **CONFIG**, and as we said previously, empty lines have a special meaning in *Une* language: they define the end of a command. Therefore, the transpiler will report an error; in fact, it will report 2 errors:

1. **DRIVER** `ClockDriver` does not define the mandatory parameter `interval`.
2. **CONFIG** is not a known command.

But following is completely legal because comment line is consider an empty line:

```
DEVICE clock
    DRIVER ClockDriver
        CONFIG
```

```
interval SET 3s

DEVICE console
  DRIVER OutputDriver
# I am a comment using an entire line
WHEN clock ABOVE 0
  THEN console SET "Clock = " + clock
```

Intermediate complexity commands

Following we will cover commands that are rarely used by novices but these commands are needed to be known even by them.

INCLUDE

Syntax:

```
INCLUDE "<URI>" [; ...]
```

Purpose:

Insert the content of one or more files (local or remote) into current file. It is really useful for big domotics installations: instead of having one huge file, you divide it into others smaller.

Notes:

An URI is one of following (observe that URIs must be between quotes):

- file:// (RFC 8089)
- http://
- https://

REPLACE

Syntax:

```
REPLACE "<literal>" WITH "<literal>" [; ...]
```

Purpose:

To replace words and symbols. If we take a look to the file "standard-replaces.une", at certain point, we will find this:

```
REPLACE "EQUALS" WITH "=="
```

In other words, the word "EQUALS" is replaced by "==", which is the *Une* equality operator. To use Spanish language instead of English, we could say:

```
REPLACE "IGUAL" WITH "=="
```

This command can also be used to define constants; which are useful for two reasons:

- (a) When a value appears here and there, we can declare it using the `REPLACE` command and we need to change it only in one single place.
- (b) We can replace a set (one or more) words for a single one.

This is an example of (a):

```
REPLACE "_MAX_TIME_" WITH "8s"
```

Later we can for instance say:

```
WHEN delay > _MAX_TIME_
```

This is an example of (b):

```
REPLACE "isNotNumber" WITH "! isNumber"
```

Note: when using constants inside Strings, we have to surround them by the macro sequence `{*<constant>*}`, as follow:

```
THEN console SET "Delayed for {*_TIME_MAX_*} seconds"
```

Notes:

- Replaces can not be nested: you can not refer to a replace from another one: if you do it, almost anything can happen.
- Please, refer to this file to learn about the standard replaces: https://iotg.peyrona.com/home_install/includes/standard-replaces.une

Advanced commands

Following we will cover commands that are used only by advanced developers or device's manufacturers. But all level *Une* users must have at least a general idea about them.

SCRIPT

Syntax:

```
SCRIPT [<name>]
  LANGUAGE { java | javascript | python | ... }
  FROM { "<URI>" [; ...] | {<code>} }
  [CALL "<entry_point>"]
  [ONSTART]
  [ONSTOP]
```

Purpose:

To execute code written in other programming languages (not *Une*). They have also another purpose: they are used to create Controllers²⁶, but this topic is out of the scope of this handbook; it is covered in the book “The IoTg Standard Platform”.

Clauses:

- **LANGUAGE:** The programming language used to create the Script²⁷.
- **FROM:** can be either a file (compiled or not) or the source code itself embedded in *Une* source code. When embedding the source code, curly-brackets must be used: pay attention to the fact that these curly-brackets denote that they have to exist.
- **CALL:** The entry point (when declared) will be invoked after code is properly loaded into the ExEn if the **SCRIPT** is marked with **ONSTART** or **ONSTOP** (also if the **SCRIPT** is used as a Controller by a **DRIVER**).
- **ONSTART:** A **SCRIPT** marked with this clause will be automatically invoked (its entry point) after ExEn has successfully loaded the model. It will be also be invoked when the script is added (injected) at run-time.
- **ONSTOP:** A **SCRIPT** marked with this clause will be automatically invoked (its entry point) just before ExEn will exit. It will be also be invoked when the script is removed at run-time.

Notes:

The **SCRIPT** command is intended to be used by advanced users, experienced developers and devices manufacturers.

SCRIPT name is optional, but can be omitted only when using either **ONSTART** or **ONSTOP** clauses. An error will be reported in all other cases.

²⁶ Controllers are the last responsible entity for managing physical devices. They are normally created by the manufacturers that fabricate the physical devices.

²⁷ The set of languages that can be used depend on the IoTg Platform version and vendor. The IoTg Standard Platform (ISP) version currently allows (more will be added in the future): Java, JavaScript and Python (notice that when using Java or Python, calls to libraries written in C and C++ can be also used).

DRIVER

Syntax:

```
DRIVER <name>
  SCRIPT <script>
    [CONFIG <name> AS {ANY | <data_type>} [REQUIRED] [; ...]
```

Purpose:

Drivers intermediate between IoTg devices and their the physical devices.

Clauses:

- **SCRIPT**: The name of the script that manages the physical device.
- **CONFIG**: This clause exposes the configuration parameters that Driver accepts.

Modifiers:

- **AS**: indicates the type of data expected. **ANY** means that any *Une* valid data type can be used (we will talk about *Une* data types later).
- **REQUIRED**: indicates this parameter must exists (be used in the **DEVICE** command).

Notes:

Normal users do not create **DRIVER** commands, they just learn about their **CONFIG** clause to know how to configure them. **DRIVER** commands are provided by hardware manufacturers.

Please, refer to this file to learn about the drivers that are provided with the IoTg Standard Platform (ISP):

```
<home_install>/includes/common-drivers.une
```

Keywords

These are the words that are used by the *Une* language and therefore they can not be used for any other purpose (like giving a name to a Rule or a Device).

Here are all, alphabetically sorted:

AFTER	ALIAS ²⁸	ALL	ANY
--------------	----------------------------	------------	------------

²⁸ This keyword is not currently in use, but reserved for future use.

AS	CALL	CONFIG	DEVICE
DRIVER	FROM	IF	INCLUDE
INIT	LANGUAGE	ONSTART	ONSTOP
REPLACE	REQUIRED	RULE	SCRIPT
THEN	WHEN	WITH	WITHIN

This is a really short set compared with other programming languages.

On the other hand, whenever you find an **INCLUDE** command you should check if referred files contain **REPLACE** commands; if this is the case, you should take them into account.

There is a set of **REPLACE** commands that is recommended to be used because it makes the code more legible. It is recommended but is not needed to be used. This set is declared in a file named "standard-replaces.une" and you will find it in all examples that come this the ISP. This file is located in the folder "include", and this is its content:

```
#-----
# This file contains the standard (default) replaces for the IoTg language
#-----

# Boolean constants -----
REPLACE "CLOSED" WITH "true"
        "ON"      WITH "true"
        "YES"     WITH "true"
        "OPEN"    WITH "false"
        "OFF"     WITH "false"
        "NO"      WITH "false"

#-----

# Relational operators -----
REPLACE "IS"      WITH "=="
        "EQUALS"  WITH "=="
        "ARE"     WITH "=="
        "BELOW"   WITH "<"
        "ABOVE"   WITH ">"
        "LEAST"   WITH ">="
        "MOST"    WITH "<="
        "UNEQUALS" WITH "!="
        "IS_NOT"  WITH "!="
        "<>"      WITH "!="

#-----
```

```
# Boolean operators -----
REPLACE "AND" WITH "&&"
        "OR"  WITH "||"
        "XOR" WITH "|&"
        "NOT" WITH "!"
#-----

# Other operators -----
REPLACE "SET" WITH "="
#-----

# Actuator and Sensor -----
REPLACE "ACTUATOR" WITH "device"
        "SENSOR"   WITH "device"
#-----

# Days of week -----
REPLACE "MONDAY"    WITH "1"
        "TUESDAY"   WITH "2"
        "WEDNESDAY" WITH "3"
        "THURSDAY"  WITH "4"
        "FRIDAY"    WITH "5"
        "SATURDAY"  WITH "6"
        "SUNDAY"    WITH "7"
#-----

# Month names -----
REPLACE "JANUARY"   WITH "1"
        "FEBRUARY"  WITH "2"
        "MARCH"     WITH "3"
        "APRIL"     WITH "4"
        "MAY"       WITH "5"
        "JUNE"      WITH "6"
        "JULY"     WITH "7"
        "AUGUST"    WITH "8"
        "SEPTEMBER" WITH "9"
        "OCTOBER"   WITH "10"
        "NOVEMBER"  WITH "11"
        "DECEMBER"  WITH "12"
#-----
```

Data Types

In order to make things as simple as possible, *Une* has only 3 data types:

- **Booleans**
TRUE or FALSE

Synonyms for TRUE : CLOSED, ON, YES

Synonyms for FALSE: OPEN, OFF, NO

- **Numbers**

- A single-precision 32-bit IEEE 754 floating point
- In the range from: 1.40129846432481707e-45
to: 3.40282346638528860e+38
- Decimal separator (when needed) is “.” (period)
- e.g.: 11 or 11.5 or -23.689

- **Strings**

Everything in between double quotes: `"This is a string"`

These are known as the basic data types.

Number suffixes

When using numbers, *Une* provides some suffixes to make easier to write time and temperature units.

As time and temperatures are quite common in domotics and as we humans have units for them, *Une* allows to add following suffixes to any number (once again: case is ignored):

Temperature:

- C - for Celsius (the default unit when omitted)
- F - for Fahrenheit
- K - for Kelvin

Example: 72F → 17° Fahrenheit → 22.2 Celsius

Time:

Managing time consist basically in:

- a) Triggering events at a precise moment.

b) Measuring intervals: time elapsed between two moments.

There is an extended explanation about this in the book “The IoTg Standard Platform”. In regarding the *Une* language, you need to know that *Une* provides the following suffixes to facilitate writing time constants:

- r - for microseconds (1/1000000 seconds)
- l - for millisecond (1/1000 seconds)
- u - for hundred of second (1/100 seconds)
- t - for tenth of second (1/10 seconds)
- s - for second (1 second)
- m - for minutes (60 seconds)
- h - for hours (3600 seconds)
- d - for day (86400 seconds)

Example: $3m \rightarrow 3 \text{ minutes} \rightarrow 180000 \text{ milliseconds} \rightarrow 3 \cdot 10^9 \text{ nanoseconds}$

Note: you will rarely use units below seconds.

What about Date and Time?

Unlike most known spreadsheets, Dates and Times are not *Une* primitive (basic) data types, but it does not mean that we can not operate with these types of data.

Une allows to manage Dates and Times via functions (spreadsheets do the same). This topic will be covered when explaining the Expression Evaluator (YAJER).

And what about Lists and Pairs?

The same as with Dates and Times: *Une* allows to work with lists and pairs via functions, but we will cover them when explaining the Expression Evaluator.

A list is just this, a set of values of any valid *Une* type.

A Pair set is technically named a “dictionary”. It can be considered as a special type of list: in a dictionary every item of the list is a pair of values (instead of one single value). A dictionary looks like this:

```
name = John Doe, age = 27, married = true
```

Technical hint

In *Une*, internally everything is an OOP class, but to make it easier to be used by people without programming skills, *Une* allows to manage basic data (Numbers, Strings and Booleans) as spreadsheets does.

For Date, Time, Lists and Dictionaries, functions are used, again as spreadsheets does.

Operators

Arithmetic

+	· Sum · Positive number prefix
-	· Subtraction · Negative number prefix
*	Multiplication
/	Division
%	Modulo
^	Power

Relational

==	Equals	Also: IS, EQUALS, ARE
<	Lower than	Also: BELOW
>	Greater than	Also: ABOVE
<=	Lower or equals	

>= Greater or equals

!= or **<>** Not equals Also: [UNEQUAL](#), [IS_NOT](#)

Conditional

&& Logical AND Also: [AND](#)

|| Logical OR Also: [OR](#)

|& Logical XOR Also: [XOR](#)

! Logical NOT Also: [NOT](#)

String

+ [Concatenate strings](#)

- Removes from left string all occurrences of right string

Others

= [Assignment](#) Also: [SET](#)

: Send (function invocation)

, Used to separate function's parameters

**** Code continues to next line (any char after '\ ' is ignored until next line)

; When a clause can have more than one item, this separates one item from another (it can be omitted if each item is written in a new line)

We will see all these operators in action in a future chapter when covering the Expression Evaluator.

Enunciations

- **Names:** A case-insensitive Unicode-string²⁹ with following restrictions:
 - A minimum length of one character.
 - A maximum length of 48 characters.
 - Composed by letters and digits in any alphabet and also underscores (“_”).
 - It can not start with a digit.
 - It can no contain symbols or special characters, neither white spaces.

Examples: Name, A_name, añothérNâmè, name23, name_23, _23

- **Literal:** An *Une* valid data type. e.g.: 12, true, “This is a string”
- **Expression:** A valid combination of names, properties, literals and operators. Similar to what we place after the “=” in a spreadsheet cell.
- **Value:** Either a literal or an expression that can be resolved to a constant. e.g.:
 - 12 + 3 → 15
 - “domotics” + “ ” + “made easy” → “domotics made easy”

<name>	A combination of letters and digits.
or	Valid chars: [A-Z] [0-9] ‘_’ (0-9: invalid as first char)
<property>	Max length: 48 chars

<literal>	Any valid data type: boolean, number or string
-----------	--

<expression>	{<value> <name>[:<property>]} [<operator> <expression> ...]
--------------	---

<value>	<literal> <expression>*
	(*) Only if <expression> resolves to <literal>

²⁹ In practice it means you can use almost any character of almost any existing language. For more information, visit: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unicode>

Chapter 3

Expression Evaluator

Une

Introduction

- An Expression Evaluator is an artifact (a piece of code) that evaluates valid expressions.
- An expression looks like a formula that we put in a spreadsheet cell. More formally it is a valid sequence of: values, names and operators.
- A valid-expression is an expression that can be evaluated by certain Expression Evaluator.
- Different Expression Evaluators can consider the same expression as valid or as invalid.
- Different Expression Evaluators even when considering an expression as valid, can produce different results after evaluating the same expression.
- Not everything is chaos: most Expression Evaluators will accept most of the common expressions and most part of them will produce same result.

Once this said, lets proceed with the Expression Evaluator included in the IoTg Standard Platform (ISP), it is named YAJER, the acronym for: Yet Another Java Expressions Resolver.

YAJER intentionally behaves in the same way as most well known Expression Evaluators do: LibreOffice Calc, MS Excel, Java, Python, JavaScript or C; among others. This will make YAJER very easy to learn if you already know any of these.

YAYER incorporates the best of all of them while keeping things as simple as possible. And this is the reason YAJER has some differences that we will explain immediately.

One last comment: in the same way you can refer to the value of a spreadsheet cell when writing a formula (e.g. `=C3*2`), when using *Une* “formulas” (we prefer the term “expressions”) you can refer to Devices values by the name of the Device, in this way, you can imagine a Device as a spreadsheet cell.

Technical hint

YAJER is a left-to-right and booleans-lazy expressions evaluator.

Une demands a very unique type of expressions evaluator because there can exist parts of the expression that will be resolve in the future (the IF clause of

RULEs).

This makes YAJER unique in its genre, at least as far as we know...

YAJER by example

The best way to show how YAJER works is by examples. We will divide them by the type of the operations.

Operators precedence

The same as spreadsheets, Java, Python, JavaScript and others.

Following table shows them sorted from highest precedence to lower precedence.

send	:	e.g.: "Hello world":mid(2,3)
unary	+ - !	e.g.: +3*2 or -3*2
power	^	
multiplicative	* / %	
additive	+ -	e.g.: 3+2 or 3-2
relational	> < >= <=	
equality	== !=	
logical AND	&&	
logical OR, XOR		
assignment	=	

Arithmetic examples

12 + 3	15.0
12 - 3	9.0

<code>12 * 3</code>	<code>36.0</code>	
<code>12 / 3</code>	<code>4.0</code>	
<code>12 % 3</code>	<code>0.0</code>	
<code>12 ^ 3</code>	<code>1728.0</code>	
<code>0.2 + .3</code>	<code>0.5</code>	<code>.3</code> is same as <code>0.3</code>
<code>-12 + (2*4) + 22</code>	<code>18.0</code>	Parentheses are used to group operations and change operators precedence
<code>(-12 + (2*4) + 27) % 3</code>	<code>2.0</code>	
<code>"10" * 2</code>	<code>20.0</code>	Strings that contains numbers and are involved in arithmetic operations, are treated as numbers (" <code>+</code> " and " <code>-</code> " operators are special cases)
<code>-8 + "10" * -2</code>	<code>28</code>	

Arithmetic with strings

<code>"caco " + "malo"</code>	<code>"caco malo"</code>	<code>+</code> also concatenate strings
<code>"caco " + "malo" - "o"</code>	<code>"cac mal"</code>	<code>-</code> also remove substrings
<code>"12" + "34"</code>	<code>"1234"</code>	Concatenate strings
<code>"12" + 34</code>	<code>46.0</code>	Because 2 nd operator is a number
<code>"1234" - "3"</code>	<code>"124"</code>	Remove substring
<code>"1234" - 3</code>	<code>1231.0</code>	Because 2 nd operator is a number
<code>"12" * "3"</code>	<code>36.0</code>	<code>*</code> and <code>/</code> are not string operators. Therefore they are always taken as arithmetic operators
<code>"12" / "3"</code>	<code>4.0</code>	
<code>-8 * "10" * -2</code>	<code>-82.0</code>	

Boolean examples

<code>true</code>	<code>true</code>
<code>false</code>	<code>false</code>

<code>true OR false</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>true AND false</code>	<code>false</code>	
<code>true AND NOT false</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>8 * 2 EQUALS 16</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>8 * 2 NOT_EQUALS 16</code>	<code>false</code>	
<code>NOT (8 * 2 NOT_EQUALS 16)</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>2 < 22</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>(2 < 22) && NOT (8 < 2)</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>(2 < 22) (4 > 5)</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>(2 < 22) && (4 > 5)</code>	<code>false</code>	
<code>(2 < 22) XOR (4 > 5)</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>"caco" <= "malo"</code>	<code>true</code>	Compared by alphabetical order
<code>"caco" >= "malo"</code>	<code>false</code>	
<code>"caco" < "malo" && (2 < 22)</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>"caco" > "malo" && (2 < 22)</code>	<code>false</code>	
<code>"caco" == "caco"</code>	<code>true</code>	
<code>"caco" == "CACO"</code>	<code>true</code>	<i>Une is case insensitive</i>
<code>"caco":equals("CACO")</code>	<code>false</code>	Use equals() function, to make a sensitive comparison

Functions examples³⁰

Numeric

<code>min(2 , 5)</code>	<code>2.0</code>
<code>max(2 , 5)</code>	<code>5.0</code>

³⁰ Later, there is a section about functions syntax and another section about how to invoke them.

<code>floor(2.8)</code>	<code>2.0</code>	
<code>2.8:floor()</code>	<code>2.0</code>	
<code>ceiling(2.2)</code>	<code>3.0</code>	
<code>2.2:ceiling()</code>	<code>3.0</code>	
<code>abs(-3)</code>	<code>3.0</code>	
<code>rand()</code>	<code>0.0 >= x <= 9.999999</code>	
<code>rand(5,50)</code>	<code>5.0 >= x <= 49.999999</code>	
<code>Format("##,###.0", 123456.789)</code>	<code>"123,456.7"</code>	
<code>isNumber("This is a string")</code>	<code>false</code>	
String		
<code>"1234567":len()</code>	<code>7 (length)</code>	
<code>"1234567":reverse()</code>	<code>"7654321"</code>	
<code>"1234567":left(2)</code>	<code>"12"</code>	
<code>"1234567":right(2)</code>	<code>"67"</code>	
<code>"str":search("A string")</code>	<code>3</code>	Index of
<code>"StR":search("A string")</code>	<code>3</code>	No case sensitive
<code>"xyz":search("A string")</code>	<code>0</code>	Not found
<code>"En un lugar de la mancha":mid(7,5)</code>	<code>"lugar"</code>	1 st char is 1
<code>"En un lugar de la mancha":mid(13)</code>	<code>"de la mancha"</code>	To the end
<code>"A une passante":mid(7,99)</code>	<code>"passante"</code>	No error
<code>"A une passante":mid(50,99)</code>	<code>""</code>	No error
<code>"My kingdom for a horse":mid("my","for")</code>	<code>" kingdom "</code>	No case sensitive

Working with dates

<code>date()</code>	Today's date (ISO format)	
<code>date():day() >= 1</code>	true	
<code>date("2021-04-08"):day()</code>	8	1 based
<code>date("2021-04-08"):month()</code>	4	1 based
<code>date("2021-04-08"):year()</code>	2021	
<code>date("\"2021-04-08\")::isLeap()</code>	false	2021 was not
<code>date("2021-04-08"):day(19)</code>	2021-04-19	Set new day
<code>date("2021-04-08"):month(6)</code>	2021-06-08	Set month
<code>date("2021-04-08"):year(2022)</code>	2022-04-08	Set year
<code>date("2021-04-08"):weekday()</code>	4	Monday is 1
<code>Date():duration(date("2021-04-14"))</code>	6	days
<code>Date():duration(date("2021-04-01"))</code>	-7	days
<code>date():toString()</code>	"2021-04-08"	Today as str
<code>date("2021-04-08") == date("2021-04-08")</code>	true	
<code>date() < date("2999-01-01")</code>	true	
<code>date() > date("2000-01-01")</code>	true	
<code>date("2021-04-08") + 2</code>	2021-04-10	
<code>date("2021-04-08") - 2</code>	2021-04-06	
<code>date("2021-04-08"):move(2):day()</code>	10	
<code>date("2021-04-08"):move(-5):day()</code>	3	
<code>date("2021-04-11"):sunrise(36.5112, -4.8848)^(*) == time("07:53:48")</code>	→ true	
<code>date("2021-04-11"):sunset(36.5112, -4.8848)^(*) == time("20:50:02")</code>	→ true	

(*) Latitude and Longitude

There are 2 ways to create a date:

- a) Using a string, like in examples above. Must use ISO format: "yyyy-mm-dd".
 b) Using numbers: `date(2020, 10, 23)`

Working with times³¹

<code>time()</code>	Now (precision = seconds)	
<code>time():hour() >= 0</code>	true	<code>0 >= x <= 23</code>
<code>time():minute() <= 59</code>	true	<code>0 >= x <= 59</code>
<code>time():second() <= 59</code>	true	<code>0 >= x <= 59</code>
<code>time("10:40:10"):hour(3)</code>	13:40:10	
<code>time("10:40:10"):minute(22)</code>	11:02:10	
<code>time("10:40:10"):second(33)</code>	10:40:43	
<code>time("10:40:10"):sinceMidnight()</code>	38410	Seconds
<code>time("10:40:10"):move(-20)</code>	10:39:50	
<code>time("10:40:10"):move(999)</code>	10:56:49	
<code>time() == time()</code>	true	
<code>time("13:10") == time("13:10")</code>	true	
<code>time("13:10") > time("13:00")</code>	true	
<code>time("13:10") < time("13:20")</code>	true	
<code>time("13:10") + (60*2)</code>	13:12:00	
<code>time("13:10") - (60*60)</code>	12:10:00	
<code>utc()</code> → Current time in milliseconds elapsed since January 1, 1970 UTC		

There are 2 ways to create a time:

- a) Using a string like in the examples above.
 b) Using numbers. Example: `time(20, 59, 59)`. Being: hour (0-23), minutes (0-59) and seconds (0-59).

³¹ Time uses 24 hours format: "AM" and "PM" modifiers are not allowed.

Working with lists

To access list items, you can use positive or negative indexes. A negative index counts back from the end of the list, so -1 is the last item of the list, -2 is the last before the last item and so on.

<code>list()</code>		
<code>list().len()</code>	0	Length
<code>list():get(1)</code>	""	Empty string
<code>2.5."hello":list("."):get(1)</code>	2.0	1 st item is 1
<code>2.5."hello":list("."):get(2)</code>	5.0	
<code>2.5."hello":list("."):get(-1)</code>	hello	Last item
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):get(1)</code>	true	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):get(2) == 4.2</code>	true	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):add(3.5):last()</code>	3.5	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):add("3.5"):last()</code>	3.5	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):add("hello"):last()</code>	hello	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):add("hello"):len()</code>	3	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):add("hello"):clear():len()</code>	0	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):del(1).len()</code>	1	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):set(1,"Hello"):get(1)</code>	Hello	Has 2 items
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):add(1,"Hello"):get(1)</code>	Hello	Has 3 items
<code>list():add(3.5):get(1) == list():add(3.5):last()</code>	true	
<code>"true,4.2":list(","):index(4.2)</code>	2	Index of
<code>"4,2,1,3":list(","):sort() == "1,2,3,4":list(",")</code>	true	
<code>"1,2,3":list(","):reverse() == "3,2,1":list(",")</code>	true	

Working with dictionaries (pairs)

In computer sciences, a dictionary is a list of pairs. The left element is named “key” and the right element is named “value”. So, a dictionary is a list of keys and values. Lets see an example: name=peter, age=34, married=true

<code>pair("power=true, red=220, blue=30, green=94")</code>	Creates the list
<code>"power=true, red=220, blue=30, green=94":pair()</code>	Creates the list
<code>pair(...):get("blue")</code>	30
<code>pair(...):get("power")</code>	true
<code>pair(...):len()</code>	4
<code>pair(...):add("name","francisco")</code>	Pair added
<code>pair(...):len()</code>	5
<code>pair(...):get("name")</code>	"francisco"
<code>pair(...):del("name"):len()</code>	4
<code>pair(...) == pair(...)</code>	true

Working with devices

As mentioned before, when working with spreadsheets formulas, we can make a reference to another cell, e.g: **=E3*12** In a similar way, *Une* expressions can contain references to a declared device name.

Lets say we declare a Sensor named “thermometer_bedroom” and an Actuator named “light_kitchen”. This is how to reference them:

```
WHEN thermometer_bedroom ABOVE 20C \
  OR \
  light_kitchen IS ON
```

Remember: the “\” at the end of a line means that the line continues in next line.

Functions Invocation

Une allows to invoke a function in two ways:

- a) The traditional way, where function parameters are placed after the function name (in between parentheses and comma separated). Function calls are nested.

Examples (the result is always 4):

- i. `floor(4.2)`
 - ii. `ceiling(3.6)`
 - iii. `min(4, 7)`
 - iv. `min(4, floor(ceiling(7.6)))`
 - v. `len(left(mid("0123456789", 2, 6), 4))`
- b) The previous way can be hard when you need to nest several functions, like in the last example. So, *Une* provides another way to do the same: using the an special sign named "the send operator", this operator is the semicolon `'`. You can think about it as sending (invoking) a function using what is at the right of the semicolon as the function parameter.

Previous examples will be now written as follows:

- i. `4.2:floor()`
- ii. `3.6:ceiling()`
- iii. `4:min(7)`
- iv. `7.6:ceiling():floor():min(4)`
- v. `"0123456789":mid(2,6):left(4):len()`

There is no difference between one way and the other way, and it is only a question of taste. You can even mix both ways. Although there is an exception: when you use following data types: 'date', 'time' or 'list', you must use the second one (the send operator).

Technical hint

Internally, everything is an OOP object and the send operator is ':'. Date, Time, List and Pair are data type classes.

Functions Syntax

In this section we will explain functions syntax in detail: their purpose, their arguments and the types of the arguments.

Numeric functions

Min

- Description: returns the minimum value from the received ones.
- Syntax: MIN(n1, n2)
 - *n1*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
 - *n2*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
- Remarks: error is launched if parameters can not be interpreted as a number.

Max

- Description: returns the maximum value from the received ones.
- Syntax: MAX(n1, n2)
 - *n1*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
 - *n2*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
- Remarks: error is launched if parameters can not be interpreted as a number.

Floor

- Description: rounds number down, toward zero
- Syntax: FLOOR(n)
 - *n*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).

- Remarks: error is launched if parameter can not be interpreted as a number.

Ceiling

- Description: returns number rounded up, away from zero.
- Syntax: CEILING(n)
 - *n*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
- Remarks: error is launched if parameter can not be interpreted as a number.

Absolute

- Description: returns absolute value.
- Syntax: abs(n)
 - *n*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
- Remarks: error is launched if parameter can not be interpreted as a number.

Random

- Description: generates the next pseudorandom, uniformly distributed value between lower (inclusive) and upper (inclusive).
- Syntax: RAND(lower, upper)
 - *lower*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
 - *upper*: anything that *Une* can interpret as a number (it is required).
- Remarks: error is launched if parameters can not be interpreted as numbers.

UTC

- Description: returns the current time in milliseconds elapsed since January 1, 1970 UTC. Note that while the unit of time of the return value is a millisecond, the granularity of the value depends on the underlying operating system and may be larger. For example, many operating systems measure time in units of tens of milliseconds.
- Syntax: UTC()
- Remarks: none.

Format

- Description: Formats numbers using the default locale specifications.
- Syntax: `format(string, number)`
- Remarks: For full description and examples, please refer to: <https://docs.oracle.com/javase/8/docs/api/java/text/DecimalFormat.html>

String functions

Trim

- Description: returns received parameter after removing leading and trailing white chars from beginning and ending from it.
- Syntax: `TRIM(data)`
 - *data*: any valid *Une* basic data (it is required).
- Remarks: if data is not of type string, it will be converted into a string using following rules:
 - Numbers are converted into their string representation.
 - Boolean TRUE is converted into "true" and boolean FALSE is converted into "false".
 - Any other data type (Date, Time or List) should be avoided: will produce an indeterminate result, but not an error.

Len

- Description: returns the length (in number of characters) of received parameter.
- Syntax: `LEN(data)`
 - *data*: any valid *Une* basic data (it is required).
- Remarks: if data is not of type string, it will be converted into a string following the rules explained in **Trim()**.

Left

- Description: returns the first character(s) in a string.
- Syntax: `LEFT(data, number)`
 - *data*: any valid *Une* basic data (it is required).

- *number*: the number of characters to return (it is required).
- Remarks: while first parameter can be any *Une* basic data type (it will be converted into a string following the rules explained in **Trim()**), the second parameter must be of type Number.

Right

- Description: returns the last character(s) in a string.
- Syntax: RIGHT(data, number)
 - *data*: any valid *Une* basic data (it is required).
 - *number*: the number of characters to return (it is required).
- Remarks: while first parameter can be any *Une* basic data type (it will be converted into a string following the rules explained in **Trim()**), the second parameter must be of type Number.

Mid

- Description: Extracts a given specific number of characters from any part of a string. The starting and ending characters can be defined as numbers or as portions of the 'data' string itself.
- Syntax: MID(data, from, to)
 - *data*: any valid *Une* basic data (it will be converted into a string following the rules explained in **Trim()**). (This parameter is required).
 - *from*: if it is a number it will represent the starting index (1 based) of the string. If it is a string, it will be used to search inside 'data' parameter and the first occurrence will be used as the starting index (this parameter is required).
 - *to*: if it is a number it will represent the ending index (1 based) of the string. If it is a string, it will be used to search inside 'data' parameter and the last occurrence will be used as the ending index (this parameter is optional, when to provided, the ending index will be the end of the string).
- Remarks: when the start (from) and/or end (to) points are out of bounds, then an empty string is returned.

Equals

- **Description:** returns true when both parameters (after being converted into strings) are identical, considering the case.
- **Syntax:** EQUALS(data1, data2)
 - *data1*: any valid *Une* basic data (it will be converted into a string following the rules explained in **Trim()**). (This parameter is required).
 - *data2*: any valid *Une* basic data (it will be converted into a string following the rules explained in **Trim()**). (This parameter is required).
- **Remarks:** the operator '==' (EQUALS) compare strings ignoring the case. This function will consider the case and therefore strings are equals only if they are exactly the same.

Especial Data Types

Besides the before mentioned 3 basic data types (Booleans, Numbers and Strings), *Une* also provides another 4 special data types:

- Date
- Time
- List
- Pair

These behave mostly like the basic ones and are used in a very similar way, but there are 2 exceptions:

- You have to create them using a function (named constructor).
- When manipulating them, you must use “the send operator” (':')

Lets see this more in detail for each one of them.

Date type

Constructor

A 'date' can be created in the following ways:

- String: `date("2022-06-19")`
- Numbers: `date(2022,06,19)`
- Empty: `date()` → today's date

Any other combination of values will produce an error.

Returns	Method	Description
number	<code>day()</code>	Returns the day of the month, from 1 to 31.
date	<code>day(number)</code>	Changes current date day of month.
number	<code>duration(date)</code>	Returns the amount of days between this date and passed date.
boolean	<code>isLeap()</code>	Checks if the year is a leap year, according to the ISO proleptic calendar system rules.
number	<code>month()</code>	Returns the month, from 1 to 12.
date	<code>month(number)</code>	Changes current date month.
date	<code>move(days)</code>	Add or subtract days to current date.
time	<code>sunnoon(lati, long)</code>	Returns the moment when the Sun crosses the local meridian and reaches its highest position in the sky at specified geoposition; except at the poles (AKA solar noon or high noon).
time	<code>sunrise(lati, long)</code>	Returns the sunrise at specified geoposition.
time	<code>sunset(lati, long)</code>	Returns the sunset at specified geoposition.
number	<code>weekday()</code>	Returns the numeric value for the day of the week. The int value follows the ISO-8601 standard, from 1 (Monday) to 7 (Sunday).
number	<code>year()</code>	Returns the value for the year.
date	<code>year(number)</code>	Changes current date year.

Time type

Constructor

A 'time' can be created in the following ways:

- String: `time("23:45:00")`
- Number of elapsed milliseconds since midnight: `time(34500)`
- 2 numbers: hours, 0 to 23 and minutes, 0 to 59. Seconds is 0.
- 3 numbers: hours, minutes and seconds.

Any other combination of values will produce an error.

Returns	Method	Description
number	<code>duration(time)</code>	Returns seconds elapsed between this time and passed time.
number	<code>hour()</code>	
time	<code>hour(number)</code>	Add or subtract passed hours to current time.
number	<code>minute()</code>	
time	<code>minute(number)</code>	Add or subtract passed minutes to current time.
time	<code>move(number)</code>	Shifts current time passed number of seconds.
number	<code>second()</code>	
time	<code>second(number)</code>	Add or subtract passed seconds to current time.
number	<code>sincemidnight()</code>	Returns number of seconds elapsed since midnight.

List type

Constructor

A 'list' can be created in the following ways:

- Comma separated values: `list("This is a string", 2022, true)`
- String: `"This is a string", 2022, true:list()`
- Using special item separator: `"This is a string" | 2022 | true":list("|")`
- To create an empty list: `list()`

Separator is used as regular expression, unless it is one single character: in this case it will be properly escaped.

Returns	Method	Description
list	<code>add(item)</code>	Adds passed 'item' at the end (tail) of the list.
list	<code>add(index, item)</code>	Inserts passed 'item' at the ordinal position of 'index' shifting right all items after 'index'. Negative index counts back from the end of the list, so -1 is the last item of the list, -2 is the last before the last item and so on.
string	<code>build()</code>	Builds the string that represents this list.
list	<code>clear()</code>	Deletes all items.
list	<code>del(index)</code>	Deletes 'item' at the ordinal position of passed 'index' shifting left all items after 'index'. Negative index counts back from the end of the list, so -1 is the last item of the list, -2 is the last before the last item and so on.
any	<code>get(index)</code>	Returns the item at the ordinal position of passed index (list are 1 based: first item is 1). Negative index counts back from the end of the list, so -1 is the last item of the list, -2 is the last before the last item and so on.
boolean	<code>has(item)</code>	Returns true if the list contains passed item.
number	<code>index(item)</code>	Returns the index of the first occurrence of the specified element in this list, or 0 if this list does not contain the element.
list	<code>intersect(list)</code>	Deletes from this list all items that does not exist in

		passed 'list'.
any	<code>last()</code>	Returns the last item in the list.
number	<code>len()</code>	Returns the size (number of items) of the list.
list	<code>reverse()</code>	Reverses the order of the elements in the specified list.
list	<code>set(index, item)</code>	Replaces the item at the 'index' ordinal position (1 based) by the passed 'item'. Negative index counts back from the end of the list, so -1 is the last item of the list, -2 is the last before the last item and so on.
list	<code>sort()</code>	Sorts the list into ascending order, according to the natural ordering of its elements.
list	<code>union(list)</code>	Adds all items in passed 'list' to this list.

Pair type

Constructor

A 'pair' can be created in the following ways:

- A list from a String using default separators: `pair("name=John Doe, age=27, married=true")`
- Same as before: `"name=John Doe, age=27, married=true":pair()`
- Same as before using custom separators: `pair("name:John Doe | age:27 | married:true", "|" ":")`
- To create an empty pairs set : `pair()`

Separators must be one single character.

Returns	Method	Description
pair	<code>add(key, value)</code>	Adds a new pair to the current set of pairs.

String	build()	Builds the string that represents this list of pairs (dictionary).
pair	clear()	Deletes all item pairs.
pair	del(key)	Deletes the 'pair' which key is passed 'key'.
any	get(key)	Returns the value (what is at the right of '=') for passed 'key' (what is at the left of '=').
number	len()	Returns the size (number of pairs) of this list of pairs.

Chapter 4

It is all about Rules

Une

Rule evaluation

Once again: every time a device changes its state, all rules have a chance to be evaluated. Only for rules that evaluate to true, their **THEN** clause actions will be executed.

Lets say the same thing more in detail: every time a device (either a Sensor or an Actuator) changes its state (its internal value), all rules are re-visited. Those rules affected by the change (those which **WHEN** clause contain the device that changed) will be re-evaluated; and if rule's **WHEN** clause expression result is true, then all associated actions (rule's **THEN** clause) will be executed.

There is another case: when the rule has an **IF** clause. For these rules, when the **WHEN** clause is satisfied, the actions in **THEN** clause will not be automatically executed, prior to it, the **IF** clause must be also satisfied: when both clauses are satisfied (and only if both are satisfied) the actions in **THEN** clause will be executed.

This flow diagram shows how a rule is evaluated (for the sake of comprehensibility, most of the internal details have been concealed):

From now and to the end of this handbook, we will use examples to explain most important aspects of rules.

A useless rule

```

WHEN time():hour IS 11
    THEN console SET "This message will never be shown"
    
```

Explanation: because this rule has no device associated (and rules are evaluated only when an associated device change its value), this rule is useless and an error will be reported by the transpiler.

In order to be executed we can simply add a timer (clock), and replace the time() for the timer's value (like we've seen previously in this handbook).

Without IF clause

Most of the rule's cases already seen, yield in this category. And as we have seen many of them in previous sections, please refer to those.

With IF clause

Triggering a Rule from another Rule

```
RULE rule_1
  WHEN clock BELOW 0
  THEN console SET "Clock value is: " + clock

RULE rule_2
  WHEN clock ABOVE 0
  THEN rule_1
```

"rule_1" will never be triggered because its **WHEN** clause will never be satisfied (will never be true). On the other hand, and as explained previously, "rule_2" will be triggered every 3 seconds. But now, the action that will be executed when "rule_2" is triggered is "rule_1", which means that actions declared in "rule_1" will be executed: printing in the screen in this example.

So, the result will be the same as the previous example, but in this case, we are using 2 Rules instead of one. Obviously, this has no sense beyond teaching purposes.

Considerations when using Date and Time

Following rule will be evaluated whenever a light changes its state:

```
WHEN (ANY light IS ON OR ANY light IS OFF) AND time():hour() IS
19
  THEN console SET "It is 7PM"
```

But for the purpose of this example, imagine all sensors are push-buttons and all actuators are lights. When a person clicks certain button, certain light is switched on or off (to become the opposite of its previous state).

It could be that no body clicks a button for 60 minutes at 7 PM (or even for days). If this were the case, the previous rule would not be evaluated.

To solve this, we can add a timer and we can associate the timer with the rule: the obvious elapse (and the recommended one) would be 1 hour.

```
DEVICE clock
  DRIVER ClockDriver
  CONFIG
    interval SET 59m

WHEN clock ABOVE 0 AND time():hour() IS 19
  THEN console SET "It is 7PM"
```

Now the rule will be evaluated once per hour. And it will work as expected.

Lets consider another case: we have to check some condition every hour and another condition every 15 minutes, so we could change this timer from 1h to 15m. This is a bad idea!

When doing this, the rule above can be evaluated up to 4 times every hour. It is not a big thing to have 4 messages saying it is 7PM, but there other scenarios were the consequences could be much worse (e.g.: pouring chlorine 4 times in a swimming pool in 1 hour).

So it is better to have 2 clocks: one that ticks every hour and another one every 15 minutes.

All that have been said for time can be applied when working with dates.

Avoiding feedback loops

Feedback occurs when outputs of a system are routed back as inputs as part of a chain of cause-and-effect that forms a circuit or loop. The system can then be said to feed back into itself³².

This is a well known problem in computer sciences. Lets consider following code:

32 <https://computersciencewiki.org/index.php/Feedback>

```
DEVICE clock
  DRIVER ClockDriver
  CONFIG
    Interval SET 1m

DEVICE cell
  DRIVER CellSetDriver
  CONFIG value SET 1

DEVICE console
  DRIVER OutputDriver

WHEN (clock ABOVE 0) AND (cell ABOVE 0) AND (time():hour() IS 22)
  THEN cell SET clock
       console SET clock
```

In this example, at 22 hours the console will not show just 1 message, but thousands of messages. Lets see why:

1. At 22 hours, the **WHEN** clause is satisfied.
2. Rule's actions (**THEN** clause) will be executed: a request to change the **cell ACTUATOR** state will be sent and another one for **console**.
3. When actuators drivers receives the request, they changes the value and send back another message informing about the change.
4. The rule receives both changes (**cell** and **console**). Console changes does not affect the rule because it is not part of its **WHEN** clause. But **cell** is, therefore the rule will be reevaluated.
5. As result of evaluation the **WHEN** clause is satisfied again and we go to 2. This is something that happens in milliseconds or nanoseconds (depending how fast is the hardware were ExEn is running). As result, there will be tons of messages in the console.

Rules must expressed in a way to avoid it.

And that's all folks